

Proposal for Faster Disturbance Rejection of Boost DC-DC Converter Based on Simplified Current Minor Loop

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Abstract—Boost converters contain a right half plane (RHP) zero. This RHP has severe limitations on the bandwidth of controllers. Further, this RHP makes it difficult to design fast disturbance rejection approaches, such as disturbance observers (DOB). This paper tackles the problem of designing a DOB based control law of the boost converter. This is done by designing a dual loop feedback controller. The designed controller is called current-minor-loop (CML) control. With CML, it is possible to make a fast response of inductor current to track reference current. Following that, the CML can be reformulated such that the current loop is considered unity. Further, the CML is simplified to make the boost converter minimum phase (MP) system. The formulated control approach is validated by simulations using PSIM software. Then, this method is verified by experiments on a boost converter loaded with resistive load.

I. INTRODUCTION

Boost DC-DC converters are used for loads requiring higher output DC voltage than input DC source at high efficiency [1], [2]. These applications often times require sudden change of load current such as when electric vehicles accelerate [1] and others [2]. Such abrupt change of load current causes undershoots/overshoots in the converter output voltage. Boost converter is a system that contains a right-half-plane (RHP) zero. Such system is also known as non minimum phase system (NMP). Conventional control laws designed for NMP systems get limited in achievable bandwidth [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], which result into poor response. Several research works studied faster control algorithms for boost converters [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12] and made good contributions.

Boost converters uncertainties can be canceled out by time-delayed-switching control method [3]. In this proposed method, disturbances and any unknown dynamics are replaced by time-delayed switching, output voltage, and current. Pulse width modulation based adaptive sliding-mode control [4] achieves cancellation of unknown disturbances. Steady state errors are removed by sensorless predictive peak current control with a comprehensive current compensation control method [5]. Output voltage ripple suppression is achieved by tracking control via total sliding-mode control technique

[6]. System loads and parameters are estimated by algebraic estimation method with nonlinear adaptive control [7]. Faster adaptations on reference trajectory and feedback is done by generalized-proportional-integral control [8]. Boost converter state-plane is transformed into state-energy plane [9] and thereby avoids using the RHP zero in control action. Enumeration-based model predictive control turns boost converter into a discrete hybrid model [10]. State estimation method estimates load current and other uncertainties in the system, and calculates a proper control input to offset them. RHP zero is moved to higher frequencies by time-multiplexing switching [11] control method. This allows the controller enough bandwidth well below the RHP zero. NMP system is turned into minimum-phase (MP) system by complementary proportional-integral-derivative to parallel-damped passivity-based nonlinear control [12].

Some of those discussed linear and nonlinear control algorithms from above have demerits such as need for actual disturbance current measurements, increasing the circuit board size, slow response to disturbances, and lack of inductor current control. This is further compounded with the fact that they require complex calculation procedures. The calculation involves many free parameters to tune. This paper takes a different approach by reformulation and simplification of the fast current-minor-loop. Then a control law based on disturbance observer (DOB) [14] is designed which does not require many free parameters to tune.

II. MODELING OF BOOST CONVERTER

A. State Space Averaged Model

Equivalent circuit of boost converter is shown in Fig. 1 [4], [7], [8]. In this figure, t is time, $v_{in}(t)$ is the DC input voltage, $i_L(t)$ is the inductor current and $d(t)$ is the PWM duty cycle. $v_{out}(t)$ is the DC output voltage, $i_d(t)$ is the input disturbance current. R and R_d are converter load and disturbance load respectively. L and C are inductor and capacitor respectively.

State space average model of boost converter is derived by averaging ON and OFF switching durations. This operation

gives the following state space model (1) and (2):

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = -\frac{r_L}{L}i_L - \frac{\bar{d}}{L}v_{out} + \frac{1}{L}v_{in} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dv_{out}}{dt} = \frac{\bar{d}}{C}i_L - \frac{1}{CR_{load}}v_{out} - \frac{1}{C}i_d \quad (2)$$

$\bar{d} = 1 - d$ is the OFF time time duty cycle. Disturbance is assumed to occur only during transients, i.e. $i_d = 0$ at all other times. At equilibrium, derivatives on LHS of (1) and (2) are zero giving the following equilibrium conditions:

$$v_{out} = V_{ss} \quad (3)$$

$$v_{in} = V_{indc} \quad (4)$$

$$d = D \quad (5)$$

$$D = 1 - \frac{V_{ss}}{I_L R_{load}} \quad (6)$$

$$I_L = \frac{V_{indc} - (1 - D)V_{ss}}{r_L}. \quad (7)$$

Where V_{ss} is the steady state output voltage, V_{indc} is the DC input voltage, and I_L is the steady state inductor current.

B. Small Signal Modeling

Perturbation and analysis of (1) and (2) around the equilibrium point of (3), (4), (5), (6), and (7) gives the small signal model. Laplace transform of this model is given in (8), (9), and (10). This small signal model is shown in Fig. 2 [18], where \tilde{d} is ON small signal duty cycle, and T_1 is the transfer function from duty cycle to inductor current. T_{vi1} is the transfer function from inductor current to output voltage, T_{vi2} is the transfer function from the disturbance current to output voltage, and T_{vi} is the output low pass filter. These transfer functions are related as follows:

$$\frac{\tilde{i}_L(s)}{\tilde{d}(s)} \equiv T_1(s) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\tilde{v}_{out}(s)}{\tilde{i}_L(s)} \equiv T_{vi1}(s)T_{vi}(s) \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\tilde{v}_{out}(s)}{\tilde{i}_d(s)} \equiv T_{vi2}(s)T_{vi}(s). \quad (10)$$

Definitions of these transfer functions are given in the following:

$$T_1(s) = \frac{a_1 s + a_0}{f_2 s^2 + f_1 s + f_0} \quad (11)$$

$$T_{vi1}(s) = -b_1 s + b_0 \quad (12)$$

$$T_{vi2}(s) = c_0 \quad (13)$$

$$T_{vi}(s) = \frac{1}{a_1 s + a_0}. \quad (14)$$

Where $a_1 = RCV_{ss}$, $a_0 = V_{ss} + R\bar{D}I_L$, and $f_2 = RLC$. $f_1 = L + RCr_L$, $f_0 = R\bar{D}^2 + r_L$, and $b_1 = RLI_L$. $b_0 = RV_{ss}\bar{D} - RI_L r_L$, and $c_0 = RV_{ss}$.

Fig. 1. Boost converter equivalent circuit.

Fig. 2. Simplified small signal model of boost converter.

III. CURRENT-MINOR-LOOP CONTROL (CML)

Current-minor-loop (CML) control is discussed here. This method utilizes dual-loop control structure [13]. The outer voltage loop produces reference input \tilde{i}_{ref} to the inner current loop. The inner current loop generates the duty cycle \tilde{d} . These control laws are given by:

$$\tilde{i}_{ref} = C_V(s)(\tilde{v}_{ref} - \tilde{v}_{out}) \quad (15)$$

$$\tilde{d} = C_I(s)(\tilde{i}_{ref} - \tilde{i}_L) \quad (16)$$

where $C_V(s)$ is outer voltage loop controller, and $C_I(s)$ is the inner current loop controller shown in Fig. 4. \tilde{i}_{ref} is reference current and \tilde{v}_{ref} is reference voltage. The aim is to make the inner loop fast to ensure that the inductor current \tilde{i}_L tracks the reference current \tilde{i}_{ref} . Frequency characteristics of current loop in Fig. 3 shows a positive phase margin (PM = 90°) at gain cross over frequency of $\omega_c = 1.2 \times 10^6 \text{ rad/s}$. A controller is designed to maintain the positive PM at a gain cross over frequency of $\omega_c = 6 \times 10^5 \text{ rad/s}$. The controller $C_I(s)$ so designed is proportional controller with gain K_{pi} . Such controller structure is selected because it will not cause

Fig. 3. Frequency characteristics of current loop.

Fig. 4. Current-minor-loop control block diagram.

Fig. 5. Proposed control block diagram.

oscillations in the current responses. The resulting closed loop transfer function T_{1cl} of the current loop will be:

$$T_{1cl}(s) = \frac{K_{pi}(a_1s + a_0)}{f_2s^2 + (K_{pi}a_1 + f_1)s + (K_{pi}a_0 + f_0)} \quad (17)$$

All closed loop poles of (17) are on the left hand plane lying on the horizontal axis. This transfer function effectively approximates unity (i.e. $T_{1cl} \approx 1$) if gain K_{pi} is increased. This is possible because in (17), the damping and response speed are given by $\zeta = (K_{pi}a_1 + f_1)/(2w_n f_2)$, and $w_n^2 = (K_{pi}a_0 + f_0)/f_2$ respectively. The closed loop poles are chosen to satisfy critical damping and fast response speed. With such a design, therefore, in Fig. 4, $\tilde{i}_L \approx \tilde{i}_{ref}$.

The design of the voltage loop controller gains considers the unity gain current loop. This way it is easier to design controller using a low order transfer function. Then the output voltage response will be given by

$$\tilde{v}_{out}(s) = \frac{C_V T_{vi1} T_{vi}}{1 + C_V T_{vi1} T_{vi}} \tilde{i}_L - \frac{T_{vi2} T_{vi}}{1 + C_V T_{vi1} T_{vi}} \tilde{i}_d. \quad (18)$$

The first term on the RHS of (18) represents the output voltage tracking performance. The second term on the RHS of (18) represents the disturbance rejection performance. The voltage controller $C_V(s)$ is designed as a proportional integral (PI) controller given by $K_{pv} + K_{iv}/s$. This controller structure is selected because of its simplicity in design and tuning. Frequency response characteristics methods are used to design $C_V(s)$ with enough bandwidth and high gain at low frequencies to ensure good reference tracking response and acceptable disturbance attenuation. Further, the resulting loop maintains a positive PM. Completed CML controller is shown in Fig. 5. Theoretical calculations and simulations done in this paper show that CML control method has a slow response to disturbances. This response can be improved by adding a DOB to the system, which show remarkable improved response of duty cycle in Fig. 6.

IV. PROPOSED CONTROL SCHEME

Proposed control is discussed here. It is derived by reformulating the fast CML control structure and applying techniques of stable inversion of NMP systems [15], [16], [17].

Fig. 6. Duty cycle improvement by the proposed method.

A. Reformulation of Current-Minor-Loop Control

This section reformulates the CML control method of (17) and (18). Results of those two control laws are that $\tilde{i}_L \approx \tilde{i}_{ref}$. Following these, the voltage response is written as (19):

$$\tilde{v}_{out} = \left(-\frac{b_1}{a_1} + \frac{a_1 b_0 + a_0 b_1}{a_1 (a_1 s + a_0)} \right) \tilde{i}_L - \frac{c_0}{a_1 s + a_0} \tilde{i}_d. \quad (19)$$

This equation is a first order transfer function for both the inductor \tilde{i}_L and disturbance \tilde{i}_d with relation to output voltage \tilde{v}_{out} . DOB can be designed easily to provide quick disturbance attenuation. However, if (19) is directly inverted, the output will be unbounded because of presence of RHP zero. Therefore, a method of stable inversion [15], [16], [18] of NMP systems is used in next section.

B. Stable Inversion of NMP Plant

This section discusses stable inversion of NMP system. Boost converter used for this study is designed such that $C \gg L$. Further at steady state $V_{ss} \gg I_L$. These manipulations result into (20):

$$\frac{b_1}{a_1} \equiv \frac{LI_L}{CV_{ss}} \approx 0. \quad (20)$$

TABLE I
BOOST DC-DC CONVERTER PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
DC input voltage V_{in}	12 V
DC steady state output voltage V_{ss}	20 V
Inductor L	5.5 μ H
Inductor ESR value r_L	0.06 Ω
Capacitor C	100 μ F
Steady state inductor current I_L	3.33 A
Steady state duty cycle D	0.4
Switching frequency f_s	100 kHz
DOB cut off frequency g	15 krads/s
Voltage loop gains K_{pv} and K_{iv}	0.9 and 3600
Current loop gain K_{pi}	0.7

Using (20) into (19), the voltage response becomes MP system shown in (21):

$$\tilde{v}_{out} = \left(\frac{a_1 b_0 + a_0 b_1}{a_1 (a_1 s + a_0)} \right) \tilde{i}_L - \frac{c_0}{a_1 s + a_0} \tilde{i}_d. \quad (21)$$

MP system is possible to be used in design of DOB based on inversion of the plant given in (21). In next section this is explained.

C. Disturbance Observer

This section discusses the design of the DOB. Inversion of (21) will result into derivative calculation. Derivative calculation is susceptible to high frequency noise [14]. Therefore, a first order low pass filter (LPF, $Q(s)$) is designed to eliminate all high frequency noise at a cut-off frequency $g[rad/s]$. Therefore estimated disturbance is given as (22):

$$\hat{v}_d = ((T_{v_{i1n}})\tilde{i}_L - (T_{v_{in}}^{-1})\tilde{v}_{out}) Q(s). \quad (22)$$

Where $Q(s) = g/(s + g)$. \hat{v}_d is the estimated disturbance equivalent voltage. $T_{v_{i1n}}$, and $T_{v_{in}}$ are the plant nominal parameters.

D. Feedback and Disturbance Feed Forward Control Law

This section discusses the complete proposed control system. This system is made up of feedback control as well as disturbance feed forward control. It is shown in Fig. 5. This new control law is written as (23) and (24) below

$$\hat{i}_{dff} = T_{v_{i1n}}^{-1} \hat{v}_d \quad (23)$$

$$\tilde{i}_{cmd} = \tilde{i}_{ref} + \hat{i}_{dff}. \quad (24)$$

Where \tilde{i}_{cmd} is total input command current. \tilde{i}_{ref} is voltage feedback controller output, and \hat{i}_{dff} is DOB disturbance feed forward.

V. SIMULATIONS AND EXPERIMENTS

This section discusses the procedures for simulations and experiments. Simulations were done to validate the proposed control approach. Experiments were done to verify the merits of the proposed control approach in actual boost converter.

Fig. 7. Experiment verification of i_L tracking i_{ref} .

A. Switching Model Simulations

This section discusses the switching model simulation. It is carried out in PSIM software under the condition that output voltage changes by 5%. Disturbance is simulated as 25% change in output current. Parameter values for simulation are found in Table I. The model was developed in continuous time and discretized for implementation by adding a switching delay [17]. Pole zero matching method was used in discretization process.

B. Experiment

This section explains the experiment procedure. The boost converter used in this study can deliver output voltage of 30 V. It can also deliver input current up to 70 A. For purposes of this research, output voltage is 66% of rated output voltage and delivers 4% of rated input current. Disturbance is simulated by the action of instantly connecting resistor banks to the converter output. In order to avoid ringing and oscillations at the output, the disturbance resistors are connected by a power mosfet switch.

VI. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This section discusses results from both simulation and experiment. Duty cycle response is shown in Fig. 6. This figure shows that the proposed approach achieves faster duty cycle response than CML approach. This happens whenever there is transients in the circuit. Proposed approach quickly responds to provide updated control input for reference tracking or disturbance rejection.

Further, the proposed approach of critically damped and faster response of inductor current was verified by experiment. The results are shown in Fig. 7. It is shown that the current response tracks very well the reference current. This is the main idea of the CML approach at high gain K_{pi} of current loop. This characteristic enabled the implementation of the proposed control approach.

From this point onward, presented results are the small signal part only. Steady state part has been eliminated because this study focused on small variations around the equilibrium

(a) Simulation response.

(b) Experiment response.

Fig. 8. Output voltage reference tracking response results from simulation and experiment.

(a) Simulation response.

(b) Experiment response.

Fig. 9. Output voltage disturbance rejection response results from simulation and experiment.

(a) Simulation response.

(b) Experiment response.

Fig. 10. Disturbance estimation response results from simulation and experiment.

point. For example, small signal output voltage is given by $\tilde{v}_{out} = v_{out} - V_{ss}$, and the small signal inductor current is given by $\tilde{i}_L = i_L - I_L$.

The proposed approach was verified against the CML approach in reference tracking. These results are shown by Figs. 8(a) and 8(b). In Fig. 8(a), simulation results of proposed control approach show faster response speed than the CML control. In Fig. 8(b), both proposed and CML control approaches show same response speed. These differences could be due to other factors and parameters unaccounted for in the actual circuit. Actual boost converter circuit contains other undetermined capacitive and inductive elements. These could all add to the damping seen in the results.

The verification for disturbance rejection speed is shown in Figs. 9(a) and 9(b). Theoretically, the proposed approach show faster disturbance rejection than the CML control, as is shown in Fig. 9(a). Faster disturbance rejection is also experimentally shown in Fig. 9(b). However, the results from experiments have slower response than the ones obtained from simulations. The reason for that could be the same as above for case of reference tracking.

The proposed control approach is shown to have good response in predicting disturbances. The results of Fig. 10(a) and 10(b) show that disturbance is estimated accurately. For the case of Fig. 10(a), the disturbance is shown to change instantly, and the estimation is smooth. However, for case of experiment, both the actual disturbance and estimated disturbance are smooth. This could be the result of other damping factors in the experiment system as has been explained above. These results verified the accuracy of the DOB.

These results have demonstrated the utility of the proposed method. Also, they have shown that it is possible to make the boost converter behave as a MP system, by action of fast response control of the current loop.

VII. CONCLUSION

This section provides concluding remarks of the paper. It has been shown that a NMP boost converter can be made to behave as a MP system. Fast control of the current loop enabled the reformulation and simplification of CML control loop. That result has been used to develop a control approach based on DOB. The DOB was developed based on stable inversion of NMP system.

The developed control approach is shown to give improved reference tracking and fast disturbance attenuation responses. However, this method can only apply to small variations around the equilibrium point. If the amount of variations become large, the approach might not work properly. It would be interesting to apply the proposed control approach to those much larger variations and observe the responses. Further, this research has shown that, there is room to improve the response speed of the boost converter. Faster response is still possible and will be pursued in the future.

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